

SCHIFF'S BASES FROM DIAMINODIPHENYLSULPHONE

BY U. P. BASU AND K. R. CHANDRAN

Certain Schiff's bases of 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone have been described.

4:4'-Diaminodiphenylsulphone is known to have powerful antibacterial properties, but it is somewhat toxic. Several compounds, disodium 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone-N:N'-didextrose sulphonate, disodium 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone-N:N'-diformaldehyde sulphoxylate and tetrasodium-4:4'-di- γ -phenyl-*n*-propylaminodiphenylsulphone- α : γ : α' : γ' -tetrasulphonate, from its Schiff's bases have been prepared and are being found to be useful in the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis and leprosy (cf. Brownlee, *Lancet*, 1948, ii, 131; Muir, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Trop. Med. & Hyg.*, 1948, 41, 575). Calloman and Raiziss (*Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1946, 53, 374) have noticed certain advantages in the Schiff's base, disalicylidene derivative of 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone against tuberculosis. As the researches of Smith *et al.* (*Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1947, 64, 261) as well as that of Klotz (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 459) tend to show that for biological reaction the drug should preferably contain one amino grouping, synthesis of Schiff's bases from 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone with unsymmetrical groupings is being considered to be of interest. These derivatives may undergo fission in the system in a preferential way to give rise to a monoamino derivative to exert the characteristic drug action without exerting the toxic action of the diaminodiphenylsulphone.

It has already been noted by Buttle *et al.* (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 110) that 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone does not generally form diarylidene derivatives by reacting with aromatic aldehydes.

Accordingly, 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone has been reacted to form compounds of the type $R.CH=N-C_6H_4.SO_2.C_6H_4.N=CH.R'$, where R and R' are different groups. In the course of the investigations it has been noticed that the 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone readily reacts with one molar amount of aromatic aldehyde and this mono-arylidene derivative of diaminodiphenylsulphone undergoes condensation easily with acetaldehyde and glucose. The cinnamic aldehyde behaves as an aliphatic aldehyde, and condenses readily with 4-benzylidene-, -anisylidene-, and -salicylidene-amino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphones when refluxed in alcoholic solution to afford the corresponding 4'-cinnamylidene-amino derivatives. (It itself also reacts with the sulphone to give the dicinnamylidene derivative, Buttle *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Jain *et al.* (*Science & Culture*, 1946, 11, 567) have noticed that the two moles of aldehyde (aromatic) could not be condensed with one of 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone. We have also noticed that a mono-salicylidene derivative could not be condensed with benzaldehyde or anisaldehyde under the usual conditions of reactions, nor when refluxed in presence of zinc chloride. But when it was refluxed with a fresh molar amount

of salicylaldehyde in alcoholic solution for over 4 hours, the disalicylidene derivative separated out in fine yellow-orange needles, m.p. 268-70°.

In the preparation of 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone Raiziss's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2763) was slightly modified and this has been described in the experimental part of the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method is a slight modification of the procedure adopted by Raiziss *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). 4-Nitro-4'-acetylaminodiphenylsulphone was prepared according to the method of Raiziss *et al.* in their preparation of 4-amino-4'-hydroxydiphenylsulphone; but this was, however, simultaneously reduced and deacetylated by tin and hydrochloric acid to yield 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone.

4-Nitro-4'-acetylaminodiphenylsulphone (90 g.) was suspended in a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (675 c.c.) and water (270 c.c.) and heated to boiling. To this solution was added tin turnings (100 g.) from time to time, and after the addition was complete, the solution was heated for a further period of 2 hours. The mixture was treated with charcoal and filtered hot. The filtrate was cooled and basified with the addition of a concentrated solution of caustic soda (50%). The 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone separated out on cooling as a crystalline, curdy precipitate and was purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 175°, yield 40 g.

Preparation of 4-Arylidene-amino-4'-cinnamylidene-aminodiphenylsulphone.—The 4-benzylidene-amino- and 4-*p*-methoxybenzylidene-amino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphones were prepared according to Buttle *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and the 4-salicylidene-amino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone was prepared by heating an alcoholic solution of 4:4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone with molar amount of salicylaldehyde for about 20 minutes. The mixture was cooled and the orange-yellow solid separating, was collected. This was washed with ether, and found to melt at 225-26°. Jain *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) recorded the melting point of this derivative as 172°.

All the above mono-arylidene derivatives were mixed with an alcoholic solution of cinnamic aldehyde (1.12 mole) and refluxed for 2 to 3 hours. The mixture was concentrated and diluted with ether. The diarylidene derivatives separated. These were filtered and washed with ether.

The 4'-amino group of the above 4-arylidene-amino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone could not be condensed with benzaldehyde or anisaldehyde. But the same of salicylidene-amino derivative readily condensed with acetaldehyde, glucose, and even salicylaldehyde when heated under reflux in alcoholic solution as usual. In the case of glucose, a trace of ammonium chloride was added to bring about the reaction. From the ease of reaction it appeared that cinnamic aldehyde behaved as an aliphatic one and had been found to react easily with 4'-amino group of the 4-arylidene-amino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphones.

Preparation of 4-Acetylamino-4'-arylidene-aminodiphenylsulphone.—Although the monoarylidene-aminodiphenylsulphone did not react so readily with a second molecule

of an aromatic aldehyde, the 4-acetylamino-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone, however, reacted with cinnamic aldehyde as well as with salicylaldehyde when refluxed in alcoholic solution as usual.

The characteristics of the compounds are recorded in the table below.

TABLE I

General formula : $R=N(4) \cdot C_6H_4SO_2 \cdot C_6H_4 N(4') = R'$.

Compound	R=	R'=	General appearance.	Formula and Mol. Wt	Nitrogen % Found.	Nitrogen % calc.
1. Salicylidene	H ₂		Yellow needles, m.p. 225-26°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S (352)	7.47	7.97
2. Salicylidene		Cinnamylidene	Yellow needles, m.p. 154-55°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S (466)	5.72	6.0
3. Benzylidene		Cinnamylidene	Yellow powder, m.p. 173-74°	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ S (450)	6.4	6.22
4. Anisylidene		Cinnamylidene	Yellow powder, m.p. 177-78°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S (480)	5.96	5.83
5. Salicylidene		Ethylidene	White needles, m.p. 162-63°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S (378)	7.42	7.41
6. Salicylidene		2:3:4:5:6-Pentahydroxyhexylidene	White powder, m.p. 243-45°	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₂ S (514)	5.92	5.44
7. Acetyl		Cinnamylidene	Yellow needles, m.p. 219-20°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S (404)	6.95	6.93
8. Acetyl		Salicylidene	Orange crystals, m.p. 243-44°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S (394)	7.28	7.1

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA.

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